

A Synthesis of Anhydrobrazilic Acid. Isomerisation of Arylidene Chroman-4-Ones to Homoisoflavones*

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A new and convenient synthesis of anhydrobrazilic acid is described. The arylidenechroman-4-ones can be isomerised to homoisoflavones by Raney nickel in boiling xylene. Prolonged treatment with Raney nickel gives chromanone derivatives. Cinnamylidenechroman-4-ones have been prepared and structures and reactions of the related epoxides have been studied.

Trimethylbrazilin on oxidation with potassium permanganate affords brazilic acid(I) as one of the products¹. The formation of this compound is highly significant as it retains one of the asymmetric centres of brazilin. Racemic brazilic acid has been synthesised² and anhydrobrazilic acid(II) obtained on treatment of (I) with conc. sulphuric acid³, was synthesised much earlier by Perkin and Robinson⁴ from the keto-ester (IX) by the action of sodium and ethyl formate. This synthesis was indeed the first example of a general method employed for construction of isoflavone nucleus.

In the present work, 7-methoxychroman-4-one was condensed with glyoxalic acid (prepared *in situ* from *d*-tartaric acid and periodic acid) to give the acid (V). This compound, termed isoanhydrobrazilic acid, has different physical characteristics from a compound of the same structure prepared by Pfeiffer and Heinrich². The i.r. spectrum of (V) showed bands as expected at 1700 and 1678 cm^{-1} and was significantly different from anhydrobrazilic acid (II) ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ 1725 and 1635 cm^{-1}). The i.r. and u.v. spectra of the derived methyl esters (VII) and (III) were also different (*vide* experimental); the iso-compound showed u.v. absorption at longer wave length showing the effect of the conjugation of the ester with the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl system. The N. M. R. spectrum of (VII) showed C_2 protons at τ 4.40 and 4.46 and the vinyl proton at τ 3.54 whereas (II) showed the CH_2 protons at τ 6.54. The iso-compound (VII) is undoubtedly *trans* (bulkier group *trans* to the carbonyl function) if we consider the mechanistic pathway to the formation of such compounds⁵. Arylidene chromanones formed by

the aid of acid-catalysts are known to be *trans*⁶ showing the vinyl proton around τ 2. The discrepancy in τ values are explicable in terms of geminal ester function. Besides the C_2 protons in (V) which appear centering around τ 4.43 compares favourably⁷ with *trans* benzylidene chromanones (τ 4.68). Because of the double bond at C_3 the chromanone nucleus is more or less coplaner as is shown by J values of C_2 protons (2 cps) because of π coupling (allylic coupling)⁸.

Analogously, chromanone on condensation of glyoxalic acid gave the acid (IV) ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ 1718, 1640 cm^{-1}) and the derived methyl ester (VI) showed i.r. absorptions at 1735 and 1640 cm^{-1} .

Experiments on the isomerisation of (V) or (VII) with aqueous alkali were unsuccessful as the compound underwent degradation to 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-benzoylpropionic acid (VIII) and formic acid.

This degradation must have occurred by way of anhydrobrazilic acid (II) which is known to undergo similar degradation.⁴ However on boiling (V) with Raney nickel for 3 hrs a quantitative isomerisation to (II) took place.⁹ Further heating afforded hitherto unknown dihydroanhydrobrazilic acid (X) ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ 1680, 1727 cm^{-1}) identical with an authentic specimen prepared by the catalytic reduction of anhydrobrazilic acid.¹⁰ Similarly, the ester (VII) was smoothly isomerised to methyl brazilate (III)

The above isomerisation was of significance in view of current interest in homoisoflavones and derivatives which are encountered as natural products.¹¹

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II, R = H

III, R = Me

IV, R = R₁ = H

V, R = OMe, R₁ = H

VI, R = H, R₁ = Me

VII, R = OMe, R₁ = Me

VIII, R = H

IX, R = Me

X

XI, R = R₁ = H

XII, R = OMe, R₁ = H

XIII, R = H, R₁ = Me

XIV, R = R₁ = OMe

XV, R = H, R₁ = OMe

XVI, R = OMe, R₁ = Me

XVII, R = R₁ = H

XVIII, R = OMe, R₁ = H

XIX, R = H, R₁ = Me

XX, R = R₁ = OMe

XXI, R = H, R₁ = OMe

XXII, R = OMe, R₁ = Me

XXIII, R = OMe, R₁ = H

XXIV, R = H, R₁ = OMe

For the synthesis of homoisoflavones, the isoflavone nucleus is usually built up from appropriate dihydrochalcones and formic ester.¹²

Arylidene chromanones are now found to undergo exactly parallel transformations on treatment with

Raney nickel. Benzylidene chromanone (XI) under controlled conditions gave homoisoflavone (XVII) and, likewise, the compounds (XII-XVI) were isomerised to the related homoisoflavone (XVII-XXII). In the preparation of (XVIII) the related dihydrohomoisoflavone (XXIII) was also formed and isolated.

The homoisoflavone (XXI), m.p. 94-95° was however contaminated with the dihydroproduct (XXIV) was evidenced by i.r. spectra (ν c=O 1685, 1640 cm^{-1}) and mass spectrum (M^+ 268, 266 ; base peak m/e 121 (methoxytropylium)).

The mass spectrum of (XIX) was examined in detail. The base peaks are the molecular ion (M^+ 250) and the ion (XXV) (m/e 121) formed by R.D.A. fission as shown in chart I. The peak at 115 is assigned to methyltropylium ion. A peak at 249 of high abundance is assigned to (XXVI) which on loss of CO gives (XXVII) (m/e 221). The other product of R.D.A. fission is the acetylene ion (XXVIII) (m/e 130) or the related allene ion leading to the aromatic ion (XXIX) (m/e 129).

controlled conditions to give (XXXII) and (XXXIII). The structures are supported by i.r. spectra (ν c=O 1678, 1610 cm^{-1}). It may be stated that in the absence of acetone, alkaline hydrogen peroxide oxidises (XXX) and (XXXI) to the phenoxy acids (XXXIV) and (XXXV).

A simple synthesis of brazilic acid was attempted from the acid (V) which could not be epoxidised to (XXXVI) even under varying conditions using alkaline peroxide. Attempts to secure the epoxide (XXXVI) by controlled oxidation of (XXXIII) with potassium permanganate in acetone or pyridine also failed. Under the mildest condition benzoic acid was readily isolated but the glycidic acid (XXXVI) eluded isolation. It is possible that the glycidic acid

CHART I

Cinnamylidene chromanone (XXX) and cinnamylidene 7-methoxychromanone (XXXI) were prepared using conc. hydrochloric acid but their transformation into the corresponding homoisoflavones were not successful. The product (ν c=O 1680 cm^{-1}) indicated the formation of flavanone derivatives. These cinnamylidene derivatives were readily epoxidised in acetone solution by alkaline hydrogen peroxide under

underwent decarboxylation with rearrangement¹³ under the conditions of the experiment. Experiments towards the synthesis of the glycidic aldehyde (XXXVII) from (XXXIII) employing Lemieux—Johnson reagent¹⁴ (oxmium tetroxide—periodic acid) gave benzaldehyde as the only isolable product ; the key aldehyde was formed as an intractable tar, which could not be purified. It is pertinent to record here

XXX, R = H

XXXI, R = OMe

XXXII, R = H

XXXIII, R = OMe

XXXIV, R = H

XXXV, R = OMe

XXXVI, R = OMe

XXXVII, R₁ = COOH

R = H

XXXVII, R₁ = CHO

that attempts to add elements of methanol to the epoxide (XXXIII) with the aid of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid failed because of the reduction of the epoxide to the cinnamylidene derivative (XXXI).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The UV spectra were determined in 95% ethanol in a Beckman D. U. ultraviolet spectrophotometer and infrared spectra in KBr disc were recorded in Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer Model 237. The NMR spectra were recorded in Varian A-60 instrument and in deuteriochloroform with T.M.S. as internal standard (chemical shifts are expressed in τ values and J in cps).

Iso-anhydrobrazilic Acid :

To an ice cooled suspension of potassium periodate (2.3 g. in water (12 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid (0.2 ml.) taken in 250 ml. conical flask was added tartaric acid powder (1.5 g.) dissolved in water (3 ml.). The mixture was stirred magnetically. After 10 min. the ice bath was removed and the whole mixture was stirred at room temperature and stirring continued for half an hour. Then in small quantities 7-methoxychromanone (1.5 g.) was added followed by sodium hydroxide (1.5 g.) dissolved in water (20 ml.). To this agitated solution was added alcohol (20 ml.). After stirring for an hour more, the whole mixture was left for 20 hr. at room temperature. The mixture was then heated on water bath at 60° for 10-15 min, cooled diluted with water and extracted with ether (25 ml. \times 2). The aqueous alkaline layer on acidification furnished a yellow compound which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave yellow needles of 4-oxo-7-methoxy-3-chromanylideneacetic acid (*iso-anhydrobrazilic acid*), m.p. 204°-05° (0.95g. ; 48%). Found : C, 61.52 ; H, 4.32. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.54 ; H, 4.30% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1700, 1678 cm^{-1}). Pfeiffer and Heinrich² give m.p. 136° for this compound.

Methyl iso-Anhydrobrazilate :

The above acid (0.36 g.) was refluxed for 12 hours with dry methanol (10 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid (5 drops). The methanol was removed under reduced pressure and residual mass was treated with cold saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The separated oil was extracted with ether (15 ml. \times 2) and combined extract washed with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). The solvent was evaporated and the

solid crystallised from methanol as long yellow needles, m.p. 129°-30°. Found : C, 62.95 ; H, 5.15. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.90 ; H, 4.87% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1705, 1675 cm^{-1}). The u.v. absorption showed a broad absorption at longer wave lengths from 300 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.88) to 345 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.90).

NMR Spectrum :

C^2H_2	4.40 and 4.46
$COOCH_3$	6.18
$PhOCH_3$	6.33
Ethylenic H	3.54
Aromatic H	2.15—3.4

Alkaline Degradation :

The methyl ester (0.13 g.) was boiled with 2% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (25 ml.) for 24 hours and then diluted with water and cooled. It was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether (10 ml. \times 3), washed with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On removal of the solvent, a solid separated, which on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave micro-crystals, m.p. 160°-61° and identified as 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoylpropionic acid. The solid was readily soluble in hot water but sparingly in cold water. The aqueous solution gave an intense violet colour with ferric chloride solution. Found : C, 58.34 ; H, 5.67. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$: C, 58.92 ; H, 5.40% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1710, 1640 cm^{-1}).

Anhydrobrazilic Acid :

The ester (IX) (3.6 g.) was dissolved in hot ethyl formate (11.0 g.) and then added to powdered sodium (1.2 g.), when a reaction set in. The reaction was allowed to proceed vigorously and yet kept under control by cooling from time to time. The excess of sodium was removed by treating with alcohol and then warmed on water bath with conc. hydrochloric acid for 15 min. After extracting with ether, the ether was evaporated and the residual oil was hydrolysed by refluxing with methanolic potash. The solution was diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. On standing the solution deposited a yellow crystalline powder, which after several crystallisations from water gave anhydrobrazilic acid, m.p. 196°-97° (lit.⁴, m.p. 197°). Found : C, 61.22 ; H, 4.91. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{10}O_5$: C, 61.54 ; H, 4.30% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1725, 1635 cm^{-1}).

Esterification :

Anhydrobrazilic acid was refluxed for 10 hr with methanol containing 20% conc. sulphuric acid. The excess of methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residual solution was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent was removed. The solid mass was left which on crystallisation gave long needles of methyl anhydrobrazilate, m.p. 129°-30°. The mixed m.p. with methyl iso-anhydrobrazilate (m.p. 129°-30°) was depressed to 109-10°. Found : C, 62.98 ; H, 5.01. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$: C, 62.90 ; H, 4.87% (ν c=O 1738, 1640 cm^{-1}). The u.v. absorption showed maxima at 242 nm (log ϵ 4.4) and 296 nm (log ϵ 4.04).

NMR Spectra :

$C^{\beta}H_2$	6.54
$COOCH_3$	6.13
$PhOCH_3$	6.30
C^2H	2.16
Aromatic H	1.91-3.2

Methyl 7-methoxychroman-4-one-3-acetate :

Methyl iso-anhydrobrazilate (200 mg.) in methanol (15 ml.) was shaken in the atmosphere of hydrogen in the presence of palladised charcoal (100 mg. ; 10%) for 4 hr at 27°/760 mm. The total uptake of hydrogen was 50 ml. The mixture was filtered and methanol was evaporated. The viscous liquid so obtained was distilled in a bulb at 260°-90° (bath temp.) at 0.4 mm. pressure, to a clear viscous liquid which solidified on cooling. The crystals were triturated with methanol, m.p. 117°-18° (mixed m.p. with methyl anhydrobrazilate depressed to 103°-104°) (ν c=O 1735, 1685 cm^{-1}).

7-Methoxychroman-4-one-3-acetic Acid (dihydro-anhydrobrazilic acid) :

(a) Anhydrobrazilic acid (100 mg.) in ethyl acetate (15 ml) and palladised charcoal (50 mg. ; 10%) were shaken in hydrogen atmosphere for 2 hours at 27° and 760 mm. During this period about 21 ml. of hydrogen was absorbed (theoretical : 20 ml.). The mixture was filtered, catalyst washed and solvent evaporated. The separated oil on trituration with benzene solidified as 7-methoxychroman-4-one-3-acetic acid which crystallised from benzene in plates, m.p. 137°-38°. Found : C, 61.00 ; H, 5.08.

$C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 61.01 ; H, 5.12% (ν c=O 1727, 1680 cm^{-1}).

(b) Anhydrobrazilic acid (100 mg.), Raney nickel (0.5 ml. sediment) and dry xylene (25 ml.) were first evaporated till 10 ml. was removed under reduced pressure and then refluxed for 21 hr under anhydrous condition. The mixture was filtered and the catalyst washed. The total filtrate and washings were concentrated in vacuum and the residual oil solidified soon. On recrystallisation from benzene, the acid was obtained in plates, m.p. 136°-38° (no depression on admixture with the foregoing compound).

Anhydrobrazilic Acid :

4-oxo-7-methoxy-3-chromanylidene-acetic acid (100 mg.), Raney nickel (0.25 ml. sediment) and dry xylene (20 ml.) were taken in a small flask. Xylene (ca. 5 ml.) was removed in vacuum and then the mixture refluxed for 5 hr. The mixture was filtered hot and filtrate was concentrated and cooled to give anhydrobrazilic acid. On recrystallisation from methanol, it was obtained as needles, m.p. 194°-95° (no depression on admixture with authentic anhydrobrazilic acid). The infra-red spectrum was superimposable with that of an authentic sample.

Methyl Anhydrobrazilate :

A mixture of methyl 4-oxo-7-methoxy-3-chromanylidene-acetate (150 mg.) Raney nickel (0.25 ml. sediment) and dry xylene (20 ml.) was taken in small flask and about 5 ml. xylene was removed in vacuum. The mixture was then refluxed under anhydrous condition for 5 hours. On working up as usual a white solid separated, which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 128°-30° (no depression in mixed m.p. on admixture with authentic specimen). The i.r. spectrum was completely superimposable with that of the authentic sample.

4-oxo-3-chromanylidene-acetic Acid (IV)

This was prepared from chromanone as before giving 4-oxo-3-chromanylideneacetic acid (yield 50%) which on crystallisation from acetic acid was obtained as yellow powder, m.p. 224°-25°. Found : C, 64.35 ; H, 4.51. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64.70 ; H, 3.95% (ν c=O 1718, 1640 cm^{-1}).

Methyl 4-oxo-3-chromanylidene-acetate (VI) :

The foregoing acid (100 mg.) was refluxed with 20 times methanol and 20% its weight of conc. sulphuric acid for 10 hr. On working up as usual methyl

4-oxo-3-chromanylidene-acetate was obtained (70 mg.) which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 111-12° (Found : C, 66.06 ; H, 4.66. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.05 ; H, 4.62% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1735, 1645 cm^{-1}).

3-(Benzylidene) chroman-4-one :

Freshly distilled benzaldehyde (4.0 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (10 drops) were added in sequence to a solution of chromanone (3.0 g.) taken in glacial acetic acid (5 ml.). The flask was heated on water bath for 2 hours. The colour slowly changed to deep red. On cooling in ice water the crystals of 4-benzylidenechroman-4-one separated which were filtered, washed with acetic acid and crystallised from methanol (3.6 g. ; 76%) and obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 112-13° (lit.¹⁵, m.p. 111-13°). Found : C, 81.05 ; H, 5.53. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$: C, 81.34 ; H, 5.12% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1664 cm^{-1}).

3-(4-Methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one :

As above, freshly distilled *p*-tolualdehyde (4.5 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (10 drops) were added to a solution of chromanone (3.0 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.) and processed as usual to give the 3-(4-methylbenzylidene)-chroman-4-one as yellow needles from methanol, m.p. 118°-19°. Found : C, 80.63 ; H, 5.97. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.58 ; H, 5.64% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1662 cm^{-1}).

3-(4-Methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one :

As before, a mixture of freshly distilled *p*-anisaldehyde (5 ml.), conc. hydrochloric acid (10 drops), chromanone (3.0 g.) in alcohol (12 ml.) was heated on water bath for 3 hr. Processing as usual, the yellow crystals of 3-(4-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one were obtained from methanol, m.p. 133-34° (lit.¹⁶, m.p. 134°). Found : C, 76.12 ; H, 5.45. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$: C, 76.67 ; H, 5.30% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1660 cm^{-1}).

Homoisoflavone :

Freshly prepared Raney nickel (about 0.5 ml. sediment) was added to a solution of 3-(benzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.25 g.) in dry xylene (15 ml.). About 5 ml. of xylene was distilled off to ensure the complete removal of alcohol from the catalyst. The mixture was then refluxed for 5 hours under anhydrous condition, cooled, filtered and the catalyst washed with xylene (5 ml. \times 2). The combined filtrate and washings were concentrated to 1-2 ml. under reduced pressure. The oil so obtained on cooling and scratching

gave homoisoflavone which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 110-11° (m.p. depressed to 87°-90° on admixture with the isomer, 3-benzylidenechroman-4-one, m.p. 112-13°. Found : C, 80.72 ; H, 5.38. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.34 ; H, 5.12% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1640 cm^{-1}).

NMR Spectrum :

$C^{\beta}H_2$	6.12 (singlet)
Aromatic H	1.7—2.7 (multiplet)

4'-Methylhomoisoflavone :

In the similar manner as above, Raney nickel (about 0.5 ml. sediment) was added to a solution of 3-(4-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.25 g.) in dry xylene (15 ml.). Processed as above, crystals of 4'-methylhomoisoflavone was obtained from methanol, m.p. 90°-91°. Found : C, 81.28 ; H, 6.04. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.58 ; H, 5.64% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1640 cm^{-1}).

4'-Methoxyhomoisoflavone :

In a similar manner 3-(4-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one was converted into 4'-methoxyhomoisoflavone and obtained as needles, m.p. 94-95°. Found : C, 76.63 ; H, 5.99. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.69 ; H, 5.30% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1685 and 1640 cm^{-1}). The compound is contaminated with the corresponding dihydro derivative.

7-Methoxy-3-(benzylidene) chroman-4-one :

A mixture of 7-methoxychroman-4-one (0.52 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.), freshly distilled benzaldehyde (about 1.0 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 2 hours. The mixture was concentrated under vacuum to 2-3 ml. and the flask cooled, and the solid that separated was filtered, washed with alcohol. The product on crystallisation from methanol, gave shining yellow needles (50-60%), m.p. 98-99°. Found : C, 75.71 ; H, 5.64. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.67 ; H, 5.30% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1668 cm^{-1}).

7-Methoxy-3(4'-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one :

As above a mixture of 7-methoxychroman-4-one (0.52 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.), freshly distilled *p*-tolualdehyde (1.25 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid was refluxed on water bath for 2 hr. Processed as usual, the ketone was obtained in yellow needles from

methanol, m.p. 130-31°. Found : C, 77.03 ; H, 5.88. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 77.12 ; H, 5.75% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1666 cm^{-1}).

7-Methoxy-3-(4'-methoxybenzylidene)chroman-4-one :

In a similar manner, a mixture of 7-methoxychroman-4-one (0.52g.) and freshly distilled *p*-anisaldehyde (1.5 ml.) in alcohol (10 ml.) with conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 2 hr. On working up shining yellow needles were obtained from methanol, m.p. 129-30°. Found : C, 72.43 ; H, 5.61. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.96 ; H, 5.44% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1660 cm^{-1}).

7-Methoxyhomoisoflavone :

A suspension of 7-methoxy-3-(benzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.1 g.) in dry xylene (15 ml.) and freshly prepared Raney nickel (0.25 ml. sediment) was refluxed for 20 hr under anhydrous condition. The mixture was cooled, filtered and solid was washed with dry xylene (10 ml. \times 2). The combined xylene solution was concentrated and distilled in a bulb at 200° (bath temp.) and 0.5-0.6 mm pressure. The distillate did not crystallise. The residue in the bulb solidified and was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 130-31°, and identified as 7-methoxyhomoisoflavone. Found : C, 76.35 ; H, 5.59. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.65 ; H, 5.26% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1640 cm^{-1}). The liquid distillate of the above experiment was identified as 7-methoxyhomoisoflavanone (XXIII). Found : C, 76.56 ; H, 6.19. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.10 ; H, 6.10% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1678 cm^{-1}).

7-Methoxy-4'-methylhomoisoflavone :

A suspension of 7-methoxy-3-(4-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.28 g.) in dry xylene (15 ml.) with Raney nickel (*ca.* 0.5 ml. sediment) was refluxed for 5 hours as before. On working up the homoisoflavone was obtained crystallising from petroleum ether (60-80°), m.p. 113-14°. Found : C, 76.93 ; H, 5.78. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 77.12 ; H, 5.75% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1640 cm^{-1}).

NMR Spectrum :

PhCH ₃	7.68
PhOCH ₃	6.11
C β H ₂	6.22
Aromatic H	1.7-2.7 (multiplet).

7-Methoxy-4'-methoxyhomoisoflavone :

Prepared as above, homoisoflavone crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 97-98°. Found : C, 72.52 ; H, 5.64. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.96 ; H, 5.44% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1638 cm^{-1}).

3-Cinnamylidenechroman-4-one :

A mixture of chroman-4-one (4.0 g.), freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde (4.0 ml.), glacial acetic acid (10.0 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (10 drops) was refluxed for 2 hours. 3-Cinnamylidenechroman-4-one separated on cooling mixture and recrystallised from methanol as yellow plates (3.4 g. ; 50%), m.p. 147-48°. Found : C, 82.08 ; H, 5.80. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.42 ; H, 5.38% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1662 cm^{-1}).

7-Methoxy-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one :

In a similar manner as above, a mixture of 7-methoxychroman-4-one (0.5 g.) in alcohol (4 ml.) and freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde (0.75 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 3 hours. The colour slowly deepened and finally became deep red. The mixture was concentrated to a small volume under reduced pressure and cooled. The yellow solid which separated was filtered and washed with alcohol. Mother liquor on concentration gave another crop. The compound on crystallisation from methanol gave 7-methoxy-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one as shining yellow needles, m.p. 160-61°; yield 0.37 g. (45%). Found : C, 78.44 ; H, 5.63. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.06 ; H, 5.52% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1655 cm^{-1}).

2-Carboxyphenoxyacetic Acid :

3-cinnamylidenechroman-4-one (0.2 g.) and methanol (15 ml.) was stirred at 45-50°. Potassium hydroxide solution (1.5 ml. ; 10%) and hydrogen peroxide (2 ml. ; 30%) were added in sequence and stirring continued for 6 hours. The solution was left in refrigerator. The solution was then acidified and extracted with ether. The combined ethereal layer washed with water and dried (MgSO₄). On removal of solvent a thick oil was obtained which solidified on cooling. On crystallisation from benzene a product was obtained in needles, m.p. 186-87° identified as 3-carboxyphenoxyacetic acid (no depression in m.p. on admixture with authentic sample¹⁷). Found : C, 55.46 ; H, 4.27. Calc. for $C_9H_8O_5$: C, 55.10 ; H, 4.11% ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1740, 1690 cm^{-1}). The i.r. spectrum was identical with that of an authentic specimen.

2-Carboxy-5-methoxyphenoxyacetic Acid :

A solution of 3-cinnamylidene-7-methoxychroman-4-one (300 mg.) in methanol (30 ml.) was treated with potassium hydroxide solution (2 ml. ; 10%) and hydrogen peroxide (2 ml. ; 30%) in sequence. The solution was maintained at 45-50° for 6 hours. The mixture was left overnight in a refrigerator. On acidification and extraction with ether (3×25 ml) and subsequent work up, an oil was obtained which solidified on cooling and crystallised from water, m.p. 175-76° (no depression in m.p. on admixture with authentic specimen⁴). Found : C, 52.92 ; H, 4.83. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₀O₆ : C, 53.10 ; H, 4.46% (ν c=O 1725, 1675 cm⁻¹).

3- γ -Oxido-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one :

A suspension of 3-cinnamylidenechroman-4-one (1.0 g.) in methanol (50 ml.) was magnetically stirred and to this was added acetone (1.0 ml.) at a time till the suspension became a clear solution. Then added 10% sodium hydroxide solution (2.5 ml.) followed by 30% hydrogen peroxide (0.5 ml.×4) at intervals of half an hour. The flask was maintained at room temperature by circulating cold water. The deep orange colour slowly faded and after 5 hours a precipitate appeared. It was diluted with water (50 ml.) and the whole solution was left in a refrigerator overnight. The pale yellow solid was filtered and crystallised from methanol : acetone (1:3), m.p. 103-04°. Found : C, 77.25 ; H, 5.54. C₁₈H₁₄O₃ requires C, 77.68 ; H, 5.07% (ν c=O 1695 cm⁻¹).

7-Methoxy-3- γ -oxido-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one :

In a similar manner as above, 7-methoxy-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one (1.0 g.) dissolved in a mixture of methanol-acetone (40 ml.) was stirred magnetically and treated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution (1.5 ml.) followed by 30% hydrogen peroxide (0.5 ml.×4) added at intervals. Processing as usual, pale yellow micro-crystals of the epoxide were obtained from methanol-acetone, m.p. 145-46°. Found : C, 73.73 ; H, 6.04. C₁₉H₁₆O₄ requires C, 74.01 ; H, 5.23% (ν c=O 1678 cm⁻¹).

Reaction of the epoxide (XXXIII) with Methanol :

A mixture of 7-methoxy-3- γ -oxido-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one (100 mg.) in methanol (10 ml.) and a few crystals of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid was

refluxed on water bath for 5 hr. On cooling, crystals separated, m.p. 159-60° raised to m.p. 162-64° on recrystallisation, mixed m.p. 160-62° on admixture with 7-methoxy-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one. Found : C, 78.34 ; H, 5.50. Calc. for C₁₉H₁₆O₃ : C, 78.06 ; H, 5.52%. The i.r. spectrum was superimposable with that of 7-methoxy-3-(cinnamylidene)chroman-4-one.

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